

Synthesis of a novel lamellar aluminophosphate $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$

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A novel lamellar aluminophosphate was synthesized and characterized. The results show that the synthesized sample is highly crystalline.

Since the first discovery of zeolite, numerous natural and synthetic zeolites¹, silica polymorphs, aluminophosphate based molecular sieves², and microporous compounds built from MO_4 tetrahedra (where M is neither aluminium nor silicon, e.g. gallophosphate microporous crystal³) have been brought to light. These materials are prepared hydrothermally and some of them possess new framework structures. VPI-5⁴, for example, is an extra-large ring aluminophosphate microporous material consisting of 18 tetrahedral (18T) atoms. A synthetic gallophosphate molecular sieve with a 20T atom pore opening, cloverite was reported⁵. This is the largest ring among the natural and synthetic zeolite and zeolite-like materials. A microporous crystalline material possessing a 20T-atom channel, designated as JDF-20 was also synthesized⁶. In the present study, a novel lamellar type aluminophosphate $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ is synthesized and characterized by various physicochemical techniques, such as XRD, SEM, C and N analysis, TG/DTA, FT-IR and ²⁷Al and ³¹P MAS NMR.

Results and discussion

The XRD pattern of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ did not match any of the reported aluminophosphates and its analogs. The appearance of three intense peaks at low values of θ (6.4, 12.6 and 18.6°) suggest that it is a short-range ordered lamellar type aluminophosphate phase. Further, it was observed as a precursor phase during the synthesis of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-22}$, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-16}$, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-31}$ and SAPO-35. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ is found to be thermally stable only upto 473 K, though the silicon containing sample is stable upto 573 K. The elemental composition is $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : 0.85 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_5$. $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ possesses a high template pore volume of 0.33 ml/g. Scanning electron microscopic picture of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ shows that, it is flake shaped with 7.5 μm particle size. It also shows the absence of any impurity phases.

TG/DTA curves show the presence of three stages of weight-loss. The large endothermic weight-loss (17% in the

range 293–558 K with an endothermic peak at 384 K) in the first stage reveals the presence of more water molecules along with template. The two exothermic peaks at 688 and 840 K are associated each with weight-loss of 8%. Compared to $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$, the total weight-loss is more (33% vs 17.9%) for $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$, as the template content is more (1M vs 0.3M for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{P}_2\text{O}_5$). Besides the oxidative decomposition occurring at higher temperatures (688, 840 K for $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ vs 633, 747 K for $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ ⁷) supports the presence of charge compensated templates in the former. FT-IR spectra recorded in the framework region of the aluminophosphate, $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ was recorded. Although, the tetrahedral vibrations around 480 cm^{-1} are not sharp, the T-O-T bending vibrations (T = Al or P) at 532 cm^{-1} are clear. The T-O-T symmetric stretching vibrations around 1125, 1173sh, 1240sh cm^{-1} are also observed. The double 4,6 ring vibrations at about 731 cm^{-1} are clear. The ²⁷Al MAS NMR shows resonance at δ 37.6 and 20.0, which are indicative of aluminium coordinated and linked to four oxygen atoms⁸. The ³¹P spectrum of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ (a sharp resonance at δ -20.2 and two side-bands at δ 20 and -60) is rather similar to that of $\text{AlPO}_4\text{-5}$ ⁹ is due to the presence of tetrahedrally coordinated phosphorus atoms.

Experimental

$\text{AlPO}_4\text{-L}$ was synthesized as follows. To a mixture of pseudoboehmite (74.2%, Vista Chemicals; 3.58 g) and distilled water (10 ml), orthophosphoric acid (85%, s. d. fine; 5.75 g) was added slowly to make a white thick paste. This paste was aged overnight at room temperature. To it hexamethyleneimine (98%, Aldrich; 5.82 g) and distilled water (10 ml) were added slowly and stirred well. The final active gel was charged into a teflon lined stainless steel autoclave. Crystallization was carried out for 2 days at 473 K. The product was separated and washed with distilled water and dried at 383 K for 8 h.

The samples synthesized were analyzed by X-ray pow-

der diffraction (Rigaku D/MAX III VC, Japan; Nifiltered Cu-K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.5404 \text{ \AA}$; graphite crystal monochrometer; computer controlled automated diffractometer). The morphology was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (Jeol JSM 5200). The framework region (400–1300 cm^{-1}) was analyzed using a Nicolet 60SXB FT-IR instrument in the diffuse reflectance mode using a 1 : 300 ratio of the sample to KBr mixture. Simultaneous TG/DTA analysis of the crystalline phase was performed on an automatic derivatograph (Setaram TG-DTA 92). The thermogram was recorded under the flow of air. MAS NMR spectra were recorded in the solid state with a Bruker DRX 500 spectrometer. ^{27}Al spectra were recorded at a frequency of 78.2 KHz with a pulse length of 2 μs and a spinning speed of 3–5 KHz. ^{31}P spectra were recorded at a frequency of 202.45 MHz with pulse length 1.5 μs and the recycle delay is 4 s.

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